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Mitigating Environmental Risks through Access to Environmental Information: A Human Rights Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This paper considers the significance of access to environmental information in addressing environmental challenges in Nigeria. Relevant legislation and case law in the UK (England and Wales) and Nigeria, is examined to ascertain whether access to environmental information may contribute to reduce the risks of environmental pollution, particularly caused by oil and gas activities of transnational corporations (TNCs). It is observed that extant statutory framework mandates certain public institutions and regulatory agencies to handle sensitive environmental data, and who are in turn reluctant to disclose same, particularly on oil spills, gas flaring and environmental impact assessment. Findings have shown that a vast majority of environmental problems which affect the health of inhabitants of host communities and the ecosystem, are caused by failure to disclose environmental information. Whilst the Freedom of Information Act in Nigeria makes provision for public institutions to provide for official information upon request by citizens, the European Court on Human Rights have made series of pronouncements to the effect that failure of public authorities to provide information about the risks of industrial activities to citizens, amounts to violation of the European Convention on Human Rights. This paper utilises a doctrinal research method (or black letter law approach). Interestingly, the Nigerian apex court in April, 2025, ruled that the Freedom of Information Act (FOIA) applies to all levels of government and public institutions. In this vein, it is argued that oil companies are bound by the apex court's ruling and are liable to produce environmental information under the FOIA, since they carry out public functions and are subject to strict regulatory framework under different regulatory bodies.

Keywords: Environmental information, Public institutions, Freedom of information, Environmental pollution, Transnational corporations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental information has been considered as 'any information in written, visual, aural, electronic or any other material form on the state of the elements of the environment'.¹ This meaning is clear and unambiguous. Different international conventions have made provisions for the need for governments and public bodies to ensure that relevant environmental information is disclosed to citizens for their safety and to promote basic human rights. In this vein, the Aarhus Convention,² provides that:

In order to contribute to the protection of the right of every person of present and future generations to live in an environment adequate to his or her wealth and well-being, each party shall guarantee the rights of access to information,

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¹ The Environmental Information Regulations 2004 NO. 3391 Regulation 2(1) (a).

² Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters (adopted 25 June 1998).

public participation in decision-making, and access to justice in environmental matters, in accordance with the provisions of this Convention.³

Also, principle 10 of the Rio Declaration, states that:

Environmental issues are best handled with the participation of all concerned citizens, at the relevant level. At the national level, each individual shall have access to information concerning the environment that is held by public authorities, including information on hazardous materials and activities in their communities, and the opportunity to participate in decision-making processes. States shall facilitate and encourage public awareness and participation by making information widely available. Effective access to judicial and administrative proceedings, including redress and remedy shall be provided.⁴

It is maintained in the paper that States should facilitate and encourage the dissemination of information on hazardous materials and activities to promote individual human rights and a sustainable future. Stookes has maintained that **'without proper access to information, the other procedural rights of public participation and access to justice are likely to be far less effective'**.⁵ In the same vein David and others were of the view that, **'without rights of access to information, environmental justice collapses and environmental law becomes unenforceable and produces discontent from a suspicious public'**.⁶ The aforesaid submissions are suggestive of the necessity and importance of this research. It is acknowledged that there are numerous environmental challenges faced by Nigerians, particularly in the oil producing communities in the Niger Delta area, and the need to mitigate such challenges through adequate access to environmental information. This presupposes that inhabitants of localities where oil and gas activities are carried out by TNCs should be entitled to demand for environmental transparency and accountability from regulatory agencies. The primary legislation in this regard is the Freedom of Information Act in Nigeria. Notwithstanding, the research explored other relevant laws in the UK (England and Wales) and a case law from the European Court of Human Rights. This approach is pertinent in view of the need to have a glance of how this important mechanism (access to environmental information) has been utilised to mitigate environmental risks in other jurisdictions.

The environmental problems witnessed in the Niger Delta area are well-known, as the Nigerian government in several occasions has corroborated on the plight of the people. In a report furnished by the Nigerian government to the UN Commission on Sustainable Development, it was admitted that:

The environment provides all life support with air, water and land as well as the materials for fulfilling all developmental aspirations of man. As in most other countries of the world, the Nigerian environment today presents a grim litany of woes.⁷

The Nigerian government specifically pointed out that petroleum prospecting with its attendant oil pollution problems has led to environmental degradation such as: loss of aesthetic values of natural beaches due to oil slicks, damage to marine wildlife, modification of the ecosystem through species elimination, and decrease in fishery resources.⁸ It was admitted that gas flaring has led to problems of ecosystem heat stress, acid rain, destruction of fresh water and forests resources in the coastal areas of the country.⁹

³Aarhus Convention (n 2), art 1.

⁴ United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (adopted 3-14 June 1992) A/CONF 151/26 Vol 1.

⁵ Paul Stookes, *A Practical Approach to Environmental Law* (OUP 2005) 33-34.

⁶ David Hughes and others, *Environmental Law* (4th edn, Butterworths 2002) 151.

⁷ National Environmental Problems, Implementation of Agenda 21: Review of progress made since the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development, 1992. Information provided by the Government of Nigeria to the United Nations Commission on Sustainable Development (Fifth Session, 7-25 April 1997)

<<http://www.un.org/esa/earthsummit/nigeriac.htm>> accessed 15 August 2025.

⁸ *ibid.*

⁹ *ibid.*

2. Access to Environmental Information

The provision of information has been classified in two categories; **passive information** provision and **active information** provision. In the former, environmental information is only made available by government authorities on the request by an individual or organization.¹⁰ In essence, it is less likely that information would be made available to the public domain if no request is made. In the latter, public authorities are obliged, either under legislation or policy to make information available for public use without any formal request. In the case of *Guerra v Italy*¹¹ before the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), the Italian authorities were liable for violating the rights to Freedom of Information of the Applicants under Article 10 of the European Convention on Human Rights 1950, for failing to inform local inhabitants of industrial hazards, safety measures to be taken, emergency strategies and procedure to be followed in the event of an accident emanating from a chemical factory classified as 'high risk'. The necessity of such information obligated by law falls within the ambit of the 'active information provision'.

In line with the substantial acceptance of the need for regional and national bodies to retain the practice of disclosing information or permitting access to public data, there is an increasing support for the idea that principle 10 of the Rio Declaration¹² has or may have attained the status of 'customary international law'.¹³ The validity of the aforesaid assertion can be verified through international case law. In the *Pulp Mills Case*,¹⁴ the International Court of Justice (ICJ) maintained that:

...The obligation to protect and preserve...has to be interpreted in accordance with a practice, which in recent years has gained so much acceptance among States that it may now be considered a requirement under general international law to undertake an environmental impact assessment where there is a risk that the proposed industrial activity may have a significant adverse impact in a transboundary context...¹⁵

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is a formal process by which a proposed activity with potentially significant environmental, social and economic costs is carefully studied with a view to evaluating its impacts, examining alternative approaches and developing measures to prevent or mitigate the negative impacts.¹⁶ It is obvious that the EIA process or study would require engaging the inhabitants of the location where such projects will be situated and in the course of such engagements, inhabitants will access necessary environmental information.

Ingelson and Nwapi had maintained that one of the primary reasons for conducting EIAs is to inform the public of the proposed projects thereby establishing a meaningful dialogue with a view to identifying and deploying safeguards to mitigate adverse environmental impacts from the proposed activity.¹⁷ In Nigeria, one of **the goals of environmental impact assessment** as contained in the Environmental Impact Assessment Act,¹⁸ is:

...To encourage the development of procedures for information exchange, notification and consultation between organs and persons when proposed activities are likely to have significant environmental effects on boundary or trans-State or on the environment of bordering town and villages.¹⁹

In light of the foregoing, it is clear that the EIA process includes consultation and exchange of information between organs and persons with regard to projects which will significantly affect the

¹⁰ *ibid* 34.

¹¹ [1998] 26 EHRR 357, [1998] 4 BHRC 63.

¹² Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration as shown above emphasises on the importance of States to maintain public awareness in dealing with environmental issues, particularly through access to environmental information.

¹³ Uzuazo Etemire, 'Public Access to Environmental Information: A Comparative Analysis of Nigerian Legislation with International Best Practice' (2014) 3 TEL 149, 153.

¹⁴ *Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v Uruguay)* (Merits) [2010] ICJ Rep14.

¹⁵ *Pulp Mills* (n 14) [204].

¹⁶ Allan Ingelson and Chilenye Nwapi, 'Environmental Impact Assessment Process for Oil, Gas and Mining Projects in Nigeria: A Critical Analysis' (2014) 10 (1) Law, Environmental & Development Journal 3.

¹⁷ Ingelson and Nwapi (n 16).

¹⁸ Environmental Impact Assessment Act Cap E12 LFN 2004.

¹⁹ *ibid*, s 1(c).

environment. In this vein, **Section 11 of the EIA Act**²⁰ in Nigeria provides amongst others, that when information provided as part of an environmental impact assessment indicates that the environment within another State in the Federation or a local government area is likely to be significantly affected by a proposed activity, the State or the local government area in which the activity is being planned, shall, to the extent possible, notify the potentially affected State or local government of the proposed activity, transmit to the affected State or local government area any relevant information of the environmental impact assessment, and enter into timely consultations with the affected State or local government.²¹

It has been submitted that although the EIA Act in Nigeria requires the EIAs before a variety of projects can proceed, there is a general perception that EIAs are seldom carried out in Nigeria.²² In the Nigerian environmental landscape, Etemire pointed out that until the introduction of the Freedom of Information Act (FOI Act) 2010, Nigeria had maintained a culture of secrecy in environmental governance with its attendant harm to the environment and public well-being.²³ This assertion is to a reasonable extent, correct, owing to the fact that the Nigerian FOI Act is one legal instrument that was long awaited, and the desire of individuals and organisations to gain access to public information has been intense; bearing in mind that the EIA process under the EIA Act is rarely complied with. It is averred that complementary provisions relating to access to environmental information under the EIA Act and the FOI Act will produce a cumulative effect on the legal rights to access environmental information.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that inculcating and strengthening significant information relating to issues of oil and gas pollution in both primary, secondary and tertiary institutions, would produce remarkable results in matters relating to public awareness on environmental matters. It is in this regard that principle 19 of the Stockholm Declaration (1972) affirms the pertinence of **education in environmental matters**. It provides that:

Education in environmental matters, for the younger generation as well as adults, giving due consideration to the underprivileged, is essential in order to broaden the basis for an enlightened opinion and responsible conduct by individuals, enterprises and communities in protecting and improving the environment in its full human dimension. It is also essential that mass media of communications avoid contributing to the deterioration of the environment, but, on the contrary, disseminates information of an educational nature on the need to project and improve the environment in order to enable man develop in every respect.²⁴

The above Declaration is classified into providing education to the masses, particularly the underprivileged on one hand, and a clear role of the media to disseminate environmental data on the other.

3. European Union Case Law on Access to Environmental Information

In the striking case of *Guerra v Italy*,²⁵ the applicants all lived in Malfredonia, a town situated one kilometre away from a chemical factory. The factory's activities produce large quantities of inflammable gas, which was said to have the potential to cause explosive chemical reactions polluting the air with highly toxic substances. In 1976, following an explosion in the factory, about 150 persons were hospitalised with acute arsenic poisoning and in 1998 the factory was classified as 'high risk' pursuant to the criteria laid down in a Presidential Decree 178/88 (implementing Council Directive (EEC) 82/501 on the major-accident hazards of industrial activities dangerous to the environment and the well-being of the local population) and a committee of technical experts found that the geographical location of the factory rendered Malfredonia susceptible to its emissions. Under the aforesaid Decree, the relevant Mayor and Prefect were obligated to inform local inhabitants of

²⁰ Environmental Impact Assessment Act (n 18).

²¹ *ibid.*

²² Ingelson and Nwapi (n 16).

²³ Uzuazo Etemire (n 13).

²⁴ Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (Stockholm) UN Doc.A/CONF/48/14/REV.I, 1972.

²⁵ [1998] 26 EHRR 357, [1998] 4 BHRC 63.

industrial hazards, safety measures taken, emergency strategies and the procedure to be followed in the event of an accident. The applicants complained to the European Commission of Human Rights that the Italian authorities had failed, inter alia, to provide information on risks and the emergency procedures violating the right to freedom of information as guaranteed to them by Article 10 of the ECHR (Article 10 borders on Freedom of Expression which include the freedom to receive and impart information and ideas without interference by public authority). The Commission expressed the opinion that there had been a violation of Article 10 of the Convention and subsequently referred the complaint to the European Court of Human Rights.

The applicants, in the *Guerra* case equally relied on Articles 8 and 2 of the Convention, with the contention that the failure to provide information had infringed their right to respect for their private and family life and their right to life respectively. The European Court of Human Rights held that the applicability of Article 8 of the Convention was established by the direct effect of toxic emissions on the applicants' right to private and family life. It was stated that the primary aim of Article 2 of the Convention was to protect the individual against arbitrary interference by public authorities, which mostly entails negative undertakings by the state. The Court further stated that the duty of the state under Article 8 also includes a positive obligation to ensure effective respect for private and family life.²⁶

The facts of the *Guerra* case also suggest that the production of harmful substances ceased in 1994 before the applicants were given essential information that would have enabled them to assess the risks related to the factory's emissions. It therefore followed that the state had not complied with its obligation to secure the applicants' right to respect for their private and family life, thereby violating Article 8. The European Court of Human right disregarded the contention on Article 2 since the state had complied with its obligation of rendering information on the risk of the emission, although belated.²⁷

4. The Obligation on Public Institutions to Provide Environmental Information

There is no gainsaying that oil TNCs are directly involved in the majority of activities devastating the environment in Nigeria, particularly in the Niger Delta region.²⁸ The Aarhus Convention,²⁹ as earlier mentioned is relevant with regard to public awareness and it is overtly supportive of the need for contracting parties to contribute to the protection of the right of every person of present and future generations to live in an environment adequate to his or her wealth and well-being, and for each party to guarantee the rights of access to information.³⁰ A question for consideration is who is obligated to render stewardship or provide environmental information under the Aarhus convention? From provisions of Article 2(1) of the Aarhus Convention, 'Public Authority' means:

- (a) Government at national, regional and other level;
- (b) Natural or legal persons performing public administrative functions under national law, including specific duties, activities or services in relation to the environment ;
- (c) Any other natural or legal persons having public responsibilities or functions, or providing public services, in relation to the environment, under the control of a body or person falling within subparagraphs (a) or (b) above.³¹

The key provisions and objectives of the Aarhus Convention are being implemented in England and Wales by virtue of the Environmental Information Regulation (hereinafter EIR).³² The EIR defines public authority to mean:

- (a) Government departments;
- (c) Any other body or other person, that carries out functions of public administration; or
- (d) Any other body or other person, that is under the control of a person falling within sub-paragraphs (a), (b) or (c) and-

²⁶ Guerra (n 25).

²⁷ Guerra (n 25).

²⁸ Olanrewaju Fagbohun, 'Imperatives of Environmental Restoration Due to Oil Pollution in Nigeria' (2007) 18 SLR 347, 348.

²⁹ Aarhus Convention 1998 (n 2)

³⁰ Aarhus Convention 1998 (n 2), art 1.

³¹ *ibid*, art 2(2) (a) (b) and (c).

³² Environmental Information Regulation (Statutory Instrument 2004 No. 3391).

- (i) has public responsibilities relating to the environment;
- (ii) exercises functions of a public nature relating to the environment; or
- (iii) provides public services relating to the environment.³³

It appears that the determination of whether a body is a public authority is complex, and in most cases, determined through mixture of fact and law. The provisions of what constitutes ‘public authorities’ under the Freedom of Information Act in the UK³⁴ appear vague but it can be pointed out from the provisions of sections 3 and 6 of the Act that public authorities include a person holding a public office, and a publicly owned company which is wholly owned by the crown or any public authority listed in the Act with certain exceptions as listed in the Act.³⁵ However, private companies are not inclusive.

It is necessary to recall that the Human Rights Act guarantees the freedom of information (a Convention right), which through case law is shown to include environmental information. In this regard, it is unlawful for a public authority to act in a way which is incompatible with Convention rights.³⁶ The Human Rights Act has defined ‘Public Authority’ to include ‘any person certain of whose functions are of a public nature...’³⁷ In resolving the question of what amounts to a Public Authority, the English case of *Smartsources Drainage & Water Reports Ltd v Information Commissioner*³⁸ would serve as a guide. In that case, the Appellant (Smartsources), a specialist business that provides information relating to pipe locations, water, waste water billing and related data in England and Wales requested a different sort of information from both Water and sewerage companies (WASCs) and Water only companies (WOCs), ranging from (1) their asset mapping database; (2) water and sewerage billing records; (3) a list of all properties subject to “building over agreements”; (4) sewer flooding register; (5) water pressure register; (6) water quality reports; and (7) trade effluent register. Both WASCs and WOCs agreed to provide the information requested under figures (6) and (7) mentioned above, where there are concrete legal provisions authorising rights of access outside the Environmental Information Regulation (EIR) 2004. However, they refused to provide information on the other categories, mainly on the ground that they were not public authorities within the EIR 2004. Consequently, the Appellant complained to the Information Commissioner, who equally concurred via a letter on the 12th of March 2010 that he does not retain jurisdiction to entertain the complaint on the basis that the water companies were not public authorities. Conversely, in the other jurisdictions in the UK, both Northern Ireland and Scotland, there is a single water company solely owned by the government. For instance, the Scottish Water is listed under Schedule 1 (paragraph 102) of the Freedom of Information Act 2002³⁹ as a public authority.

The Appellant thereafter approached the Upper Tribunal (Administrative Appeals Chamber), where the appeal was dismissed. The primary issue for determination in the Smartsources case, therefore, was whether a privatised water company is a public Authority for the purposes of the Environmental Information Regulations? This was answered in the negative. In coming to its conclusion, the Tribunal had taken a plethora of judicial cases into consideration. The Tribunal had given credence and made reference to the case of *Cameron v Network Rail Infrastructure Ltd*,⁴⁰ where a High Court held that Network Rail Infrastructure Ltd, a private company rendering public services was neither a core nor a hybrid public authority for the purposes of section 6(3) of the Human Rights Act 1998. The Tribunal equally submitted to the argument that in determining a ‘Public Authority’ under Regulation 2(2)(c), the focus of the Court is not necessarily whether the body is public or private, but whether the body is carrying out functions of a public nature.⁴¹ However, the Tribunal admits that the ambit of Regulation 2(2)(c) as mentioned earlier is narrower than the scope of the Human Rights Act which referred to public authorities as ‘persons certain of whose functions are functions of a public nature...’ This, according to the Tribunal is suggestive that a body may be a public authority for the purpose of

³³ EIR (n 32) Regulations 2(2)(a) (c) and (d).

³⁴ Freedom of Information Act 2000.

³⁵ FoIA UK (n 34), s 3 (1) and s 6(1)(a) and (b).

³⁶ Human Rights Act 1998, s 6(1).

³⁷ *ibid* s 6(3).

³⁸ [2010] UKUT 415 AAC, Upper Tribunal (Administrative Appeals Chamber).

³⁹ Freedom of Information (Scotland) Act 2002.

⁴⁰ [2006] EWHC 1133 (QB).

⁴¹ *Smartsources case* (n 38) [55].

the Human Rights Act and yet still fall outside Regulation 2(2)(c) of the EIR.⁴² Due regard was given to the fact that the mere existence of an intensive regulatory regime does not translate that the provision of the service is a function of public nature. The Tribunal noted that several of the water companies can buy each other, or buy parts of each other subject to competition legislation, and this is a pointer to the fact that the water companies are not public authorities.⁴³

Looking at the key principles in the *Smartsource* case, it may be submitted that oil TNCs are not likely to be considered as public authorities for the purposes of the Environmental Information Regulation and the Human Rights Act 1998. This position would be justified on the grounds that oil companies are basically carrying out functions of a private nature and they do retain the discretion of selling off major share or stakes, and their activities are only governed by government regulations or laws. Conversely, it has been shown from the *Smartsource* case that the determination of whether a company is a public authority or not is complex, particularly in circumstances where Oil Companies are jointly owned by government and private entities. Furthermore, TNCs, although are basically private entities, they do play public roles. By virtue of the Freedom of Information Act in Nigeria, Public Institution has been defined as:

...Any legislative, executive, judicial, administrative or advisory body of the government, including boards, bureau, committees or commissions of the State, and any subsidiary body of those body including but not limited to committees and sub-committees which are supported in whole or in part by public fund or which expends public fund and private bodies providing public services, performing public functions or utilizing public funds.⁴⁴

A combined reading of the Environmental Information Act in England and Wales, the Human Rights Act 1998 in UK, and the Freedom of Information Act 2011 in Nigeria, points to the fact that apart from government departments, institutions performing public functions are legally bound to provide information on request by applicants. Madichie, a legal adviser to the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC) observed that the NNPC, being a statutory corporation, does not fall within the ambit of a Public Institution as defined by the FoI Act.⁴⁵ This stance was described by the Vanguard as a 'strange response'. However, the then group managing director of the Corporation had debunked the position of the legal adviser, maintaining that the NNPC abides by the provisions of the FoI Act.⁴⁶ Ordinarily, there ought not to be any ambiguity on whether a government corporation such as NNPC (now NNPC Limited, including its subsidiary companies) falls within a 'public institution' as defined by the Freedom of Information Act, this is primarily anchored on the grounds that the Corporation is supported by public fund and it expends public fund, and it is the main representative of government in the petroleum sector. Also, the Department of Petroleum Resources, which has been scrapped, a former department within the Federal Ministry of Petroleum, which was saddled with the duty to establish and enforce environmental regulations, was a key government department where tangible environmental information would be obtained.⁴⁷ Or better still, the National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA),⁴⁸ which is actively involved in incidents of oil spills in Nigeria would practically be a warehouse for environmental information to be retrieved through the instrumentality of the FoI Act.

Just recently (in April 2025) the Supreme Court of Nigeria ruled in *Osakwe and 8 Ors v EDOSACA*,⁴⁹ that the Freedom of Information Act, regardless of the level of government, is applicable to any public official, agency, or institution. It is maintained that the landmark ruling in the aforementioned

⁴²*Smartsource* case (n 38) [63].

⁴³*Smartsource* (n 38) [64].

⁴⁴ Freedom of Information Act 2011 No. 4, s 31.

⁴⁵ Vanguard News, 'NNPC and the FoI Act' (Nigeria, 22 August 2012) <<http://www.vanguardngr.com/2012/08/nnpc-and-the-foi-act/>> accessed 5 February 2025.

⁴⁶ *ibid.*

⁴⁷ Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation, 'About NNPC' <<http://nnpcgroup.com/AboutNNPC/CorporateInfo.aspx>> accessed 4 August 2025. Following the enactment of the Petroleum Industry Act, the Department of Petroleum Resources has been transitioned to the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission, the Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Regulatory Authority.

⁴⁸ National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency <<http://nosdra.org.ng/>> accessed 4 August 2025.

⁴⁹ Unreported (Suit No. SC/614/2018) April 2025

Osakwe's case will promote environmental accountability, and allow for better environmental justice system and protection, through proper disclosures on gas flaring data and oil spills from TNCs.

It is submitted that even if the Nigerian subsidiaries of oil TNCs can be seen as private companies excluded from the FoI Act, it is clear that the Nigerian government through its representative agencies and corporations in the oil industry will be legally obliged to provide environmental information to the public, since it is clear that government has major stakes in all private oil companies. Furthermore, legislators may want to demystify the conundrum of specific organisations that constitute 'public authorities' by listing such bodies, as it is the case in Schedule 1 of the Freedom of Information (Scotland) Act mentioned above.⁵⁰

It appears that a vast majority of inhabitants of oil producing areas are not inclined to request environmental information from TNCs, and this neglect in accessing environmental information is a general shortcoming even amongst the media. Ajibola observed that for a country whose budget is funded by the proceeds of sale of oil and gas, it is expected that the media would constantly demand transparency and accountability in the oil and gas sector, but this is not the case, rather, the petroleum industry in Nigeria is seen as the most secretive business environment in Nigeria.⁵¹ This latter position could be associated with the lack of enforcement or inadequate awareness on extant laws and procedures to access information.

It is noted that existing legislation on access to environmental information are basically passive in nature, that is, information is not likely to be given freely to inhabitants except on request. With regards to the sort of dangerous environmental activities in the Niger Delta, it would be imperative for public authorities to be obliged, either under legislation or policy to make information available for the public use without any formal request by citizens.

Looking at Article 9(1) of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act,⁵² which states that 'every individual shall have the right to receive information', it would seem that the provision can be interpreted as generating both passive and active rights to access environmental information. Again, this provision, bordering on fundamental rights, could not be seen to exonerate private oil multinationals on the obligation to provide information. In view of this, it will be correct to submit that Article 9 above can be invoked against oil TNCs where they fail to provide environmental information, provided the applicant can show that such information is one that would affect his person, in essence there must be a reasonable cause of action. This is because, both fundamental rights provisions in the Nigerian Constitution⁵³ and the African Charter are to be expansively and purposely interpreted by the Courts with a view to advancing and realising the rights and freedoms contained in them.⁵⁴

Despite the legal mandates with regards to the provision of environmental information, government has a positive duty to provide information for the well-being of the citizenry, this is pertinent, owing to the *Public Trust Doctrine* in environmental matters where the State is considered as a trustee of all natural resources,⁵⁵ and this duty, no doubt entails a preservation of the environment which man is at the centre. The National Policy on the Environment which defines a framework for environmental governance in Nigeria recognises in its Action Plan the need for environmental reporting in the management of natural resources as well as embarking on environmental impact assessment for major development project.⁵⁶ It is maintained that these plans, if fully implemented as equally incorporated in various statutes mentioned, would sufficiently provide environmental information at the threshold of inhabitants. Despite the sufficient presence of legal and institutional framework, there is a disappointing reluctance to implement on the parts of the government and oil TNCs.

⁵⁰ See FOI (Scotland) Act (n 39).

⁵¹ Ajibola Amzat, 'Poor media coverage of oil-gas industry' *The Guardian* (Nigeria, 19 March 2015) <<http://guardian.ng/opinion/poor-media-coverage-of-oil-gas-industry/>> accessed 10 August 2015.

⁵² Cap A9 LFN 2004.

⁵³ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) part IV.

⁵⁴ Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules, 2009 Preamble 3(a).

⁵⁵ The National Policy on Environment, Nigeria 'Guiding Principles' (1999) para 1.5

<<http://www.environment.gov.ng/index.php/downloads/6-national-policy-on-environment>> accessed 4 August 2015.

⁵⁶ The National Policy on Environment (n 55) 7.

At the 9th National Council on Environment 2013, the Bayelsa State government had alleged the failure of Chevron Nigeria Limited to comply with provisions of the Environmental Impact Assessment Act 1992, by embarking on a drilling project without EIA and the eventual damage to the environment by gas explosion in the course of the drilling.⁵⁷ In response, the Council had agreed to urge the Federal Ministry of Environment to take urgent action.⁵⁸ It would be surprising to witness a TNC embarking on such a sensitive project without carrying out due consultations under the EIA Act. This is a reflection of some of the challenges or level of impunity witnessed in the relationship between oil operators and the host communities. Such impunity undermines the right to access environmental information and others.

5. Education in Environmental Matters

Looking at the challenges encountered in accessing environmental information from oil operators and government agencies, it is expedient to explore other feasible means to ensure that environmental information gets to the hinterland, particularly host communities to oil and gas activities. It is observed that inculcating and strengthening significant information relating to issues of oil and gas pollution in both primary, secondary and tertiary institutions, would produce better results than some of the statutory means mentioned earlier. It is in this regard that principle 19 of the Stockholm Declaration (1972) affirms the pertinence of education in environmental matters. It provides that:

Education in environmental matters, for the younger generation as well as adults, giving due consideration to the underprivileged, is essential in order to broaden the basis for an enlightened opinion and responsible conduct by individuals, enterprises and communities in protecting and improving the environment in its full human dimension. It is also essential that mass media of communications avoid contributing to the deterioration of the environment, but, on the contrary, disseminates information of an educational nature on the need to project and improve the environment in order to enable man develop in every respect.⁵⁹

The above Declaration is divided into providing education to the masses, particularly the underprivileged on one hand, and an explicit role of the media to disseminate environmental information on the other. Whilst the latter is silent on whose duty it is to provide environmental education, it could be assumed that such burden will be shared by government and major industries.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper examines the significance of access to environmental information in addressing environmental challenges in Nigeria. Relevant legislation and case law in the UK (England and Wales) and Nigeria, is examined to ascertain whether access to environmental information may contribute to reduce the risks of environmental pollution, particularly caused by oil and gas activities of transnational corporations (TNCs). It is observed that while the legal framework exists regarding access to environmental information, enforcement has been weak, and oil companies sometimes fail to adequately disclose environmental impacts. Notwithstanding, it has been pointed out that government has a positive duty to provide information for the well-being of the citizenry, this is pertinent, owing to the *Public Trust Doctrine* in environmental matters where the State is considered as a trustee of all natural resources, and this duty, no doubt entails a preservation of the environment which man is at the centre. Whilst there could be contentions as to whether private companies engaged in environmental activities are bound by extant legal framework on access to environmental information to disclosed environmental information, requests can be made directly to public institutions holding the information, such as the National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA), Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission, the Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Regulatory Authority.

⁵⁷ Federal Ministry of Environment, General Report for the 9th National Council on Environment, Themed 'Green Economy-A Panacea for Sustainable Development' 5th – 10th May 2013 (Memo No. 10: FMENV/9TH/NCE/STATE/BAY/EA&R/010) p16.

⁵⁸ Federal Ministry of Environment, General Report (n 57).

⁵⁹ Stockholm Declaration (n 24).